

Use solar sheets to constrain the solar spectra to produce a very strong peak directly corresponding to the ideal wavelength of the solar panel.

Solar sheet design (1 sheet):

- functional top: sits below topmost perimeter, has AR coating to prevent reflection loss
- perimeter layer: thin layer of glass with bottom layer reflecting the wavelength of your template and top layer reflects all light back in; acts as fibre optic for template photons and a cavity for all others
- main body: uses n-type doped phosphorus glass to create a sea of electrons; this directly produces plasmon effects which reduce the distributions of spectra
 - we use high quality refractive glass to increase the duration of time that photons spend that can interact with electrons as well as acting as a containing cavity - this allows orders of magnitude more effective collisions
 - we also inject electrons into the insulating glass to improve efficiency (but doping is still required for stability)
 - plasmon effects thermalise the photons to oscillate about the mean - photons that land at exactly the template wavelength is captured by the perimeter layer
- bottom recombination: sits below lower perimeter layer, recombines the template photons (which act to spike and skew the distribution) with the nondeviant photons affected by plasmon effects

By stacking multiple solar sheets, you can cleanly reduce the solar spectra to an identifiable monochromatic peak(s). It is merely an addition on top of a solar panel, not necessarily something drastically altering.

